

Calibration and analysis of the telluric O₂-bands

a spectropolarimetric approach for aerosol and cloud analysis

Michael Sterzik, European Southern Observatory
Stefano Bagnulo, Armagh Observatory
Claudia Emde, Meteorological Institute, LMU, Munich
Daphne Stam, TU Delft

Observatory/Astronomy relevance

:

beyond atmosphere classification (transparency/seeing/PWV)

- telluric calibration (molecfit)
- forecasting (wind, turbulence, IQ, -> meteorology)
- predictive scheduling
- exo-Earth atmosphere characterisation

Earth Cloud Systems

Variety of Aerosols

Sea Spray Aerosols (SSA)

T. Wilson et al. Nature 525, 234-238 (2015):
A Marine biogenic source of atmospheric ice-nucleating particles

Polarimetric Signatures of Planet Earth

rainbow polarization

Hansen, J. E. & Hovenier, J. W. Interpretation of the polarization of Venus. *Journal of Atmospheric Science* **31**, 1137–1160 (1974).

Bréon, F. M. & Goloub, P. Cloud droplet effective radius from spaceborne polarization measurements. *Geophysical research letters* **25**, 1879–1882 (1998).

Bailey, J. Rainbows, Polarization, and the Search for Habitable Planets. *Astrobiology* **7**, 320–332 (2007).

Polarimetric Signatures of Planet Earth

pure ocean surface

Phase Angle

pure land surface

Phase Angle

no clouds

clouds

McCullough, P. R. Models of Polarized Light from Oceans and Atmospheres of Earth-like Extrasolar Planets. *arXiv astro-ph*, (2006).

Williams, D. M. & Gaidos, E. Detecting the glint of starlight on the oceans of distant planets. *Icarus* **195**, 927–937 (2008).

Modelling Earth's Polarization

VRT calc. include

atmosphere
geometry
surfaces

missing
inhomogenities
realistic clouds
aerosols/haze
realistic surfaces

Earthshine

Spectropolarimetry of ES:

Observing Date	25-Apr-2011:UT09	10-Jun-2011:UT01
View of Earth as seen from the Moon	<p>10 June 2011, 01:00 UTC</p>	
Sun-Earth-Moon phase	87 deg	102 deg
ocean fraction in Earthshine	18%	46%
vegetation fraction in Earthshine	7%	3%
tundra, shrub, ice and desert fraction in Earthshine	3%	1%
total cloud fraction in Earthshine	72%	50%
cloud fraction $t > 6$	40%	27%

line vers. continuum

25-Apr-2011:UT09

10-Jun-2011:UT01

D. Stams model spectra (3nm resolution) agree qualitatively with the measurements (1nm): O2A strength, water, NDVI.

MYSTIC 3D-vec. rad. transfer

w/ C. Emde (Monte Carlo code for the physically correct Tracing of photons In Cloudy atmospheres)

Emde, C., Buras, R., Mayer, B. & Blumthaler, M. The impact of aerosols on polarized sky radiance: **model development, validation, and applications**. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* 10, 383–396–396 (2010).

Emde, C., Buras, R. & Mayer, B. An efficient method to compute **high spectral resolution** polarized solar radiances using the **Monte Carlo** approach. *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer* 112, 1622–1631 (2011).

surface type:
| Lambert 0.0 | Lambert 0.2 | Lambert 1.0 | Ocean / Fresnel | Gras / Forest

We'd like high spectral resolution

accurate simulation with instrument filter function (FWHM~3nm)

absorption parameterization with different spectral resolutions

Sensitivity of high altitude clouds

ES modelling vers.2

Earthshine O2-A observed

Earthshine O2-A observed

Signal and Background around the Lunar Limb

More (Spectro-)Polarimetry of ES

of ES

Bazzon, A., Schmid, H. M. & Gisler, D. Measurement of the earthshine polarization in the B, V, R, and I band as **function of phase**. *arXiv astro-ph.EP*, (2013).

Takahashi, J. *et al.* **Phase Variation** of Earthshine Polarization Spectra. *Publications of the Astronomical Society of Japan* **65**, 38 (2013).

Miles-Páez, P. A., Pallé, E. & Zapatero Osorio, M. R. Simultaneous optical and **near-infrared** linear spectropolarimetry of the earthshine. *A&A* **562**, L5 (2014).

Spectral fine-structure in the polarisation of skylight

I. Aben¹, F. Helderma¹, D.M. Stam^{2,3,4}, and P. Stammes³

Figure 1. The degree of linear polarisation of the cloud-free zenith sky as a function of wavelength from 305 to 794 nm, for three values of the solar zenith angle (SZA), as measured at SRON, Utrecht, The Netherlands (52.1°N, 5.2°E) on the morning of April, 7, 1997. Superimposed on the broad-band continuum, spectral fine-structure in the polarisation is observed.

Figure 3. The UV part of the zenith sky polarisation spectrum for SZA = 79° is shown in more detail (top). The spectral fine-structure in the measured polarisation coincides closely with the Fraunhofer lines in the extra-terrestrial solar irradiance spectrum (bottom). The latter has been measured on April, 7, 1997, by GOME on ERS-2. Even the smallest spectral features in the polarisation coincide with Fraunhofer lines, which demonstrates the precision ($\sim 10^{-3}$) of the measurements.

Spectropolarimetry of our Sky

Polarization of skylight in the O₂A band: effects of aerosol properties

Eyk Boesche,^{1,*} Piet Stammes,^{2,4} Réne Preusker,¹ Ralf Bennartz,^{3,5}
Wouter Knap,² and Juergen Fischer¹

Fig. 11. Degree of linear polarization of zenith skylight as a function of wavelength at a solar zenith angle of $\theta_0 = 65^\circ$ for two different spectral response functions and different altitudes of the elevated scattering layer. The boundary layer comprises Aerosol₁ and optical thickness of $\tau_{BL} = 0.048$ and the elevated layer comprises scatterer C_1 with $\tau_{EL} = 0.100$. The elevated layer is shifted through the atmosphere from 2 to 16 km in steps of two kilometers, resulting in a decrease of P_b with increasing altitude of the elevated layer.

Spectropolarimetry of our Sky

Spectropolarimetry of our Sky

Proposal: SpecPols of Zenith Sky

- use FORS2pol and HARPSpol @ high spectral resolution
- monitoring of sunset sky-flats
- retrieve aerosol and cirrus content, composition, and height distribution with VRT model
- timescale of variability (stability)
- correlate with extinction
- correlate with local (mining) and global (volcano) effects
- validate retrieval code for the local (zenith) patch
- apply to Earthshine skybackground/global retrieval